

Organic-inorganic catalytic separator for robust Li-S batteries via ethanedithiol-functionalized VSe₂ with ligand strategy

Kaifu Lin^{a, b}, Chaoqi Zhang^{a, **}, Ban Fei^b, Jing Yu^{c, d}, Canhuang Li^c, Qidi Chen^a, Daoping Cai^a, Baisheng Sa^a, Wenwei Chen^a, Dawei Yang^e, Jordi Arbiol^{d, f}, Andreu Cabot^{c, f, *}, Hongbing Zhan^{a, **}

^a College of Materials Science and Engineering, Fuzhou University, Fuzhou 350108, China

^b Department of Mechanical Engineering and Research Institute for Smart Energy, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong 999077, China

^c Catalonia Institute for Energy Research-IREC, Sant Adrià de Besòs, 08930, Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain

^d Catalan Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology (ICN2), CSIC and BIST, Campus UAB, Bellaterra, 08193, Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain

^e Henan Province Key Laboratory of Photovoltaic Materials, School of Future Technology, Henan University, Kaifeng 475004, China

^f ICREA, Pg. Lluís Companys 23, 08010, Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Overcoming polysulfide shuttling and sluggish sulfur electrochemistry remains pivotal for viable lithium-sulfur batteries. Herein, we develop an organic-inorganic catalytic interface engineered through molecular anchoring of ethanedithiol (EDT) on VSe₂ nanosheets (SH-VSe₂), which concurrently tailors the electronic structure and mediates dynamic redox processes. EDT coordination upshifts the d-band center of vanadium sites, strengthening polysulfide chemisorption while enhancing intrinsic catalytic activity. Critically, the surface-tethered EDT operates as a non-migratory redox mediator, drastically reducing Li₂S nucleation/dissolution barriers through forming -SLi intermediate. When this catalyst is located at the cell separator, this synergistic design enables to transcend conventional adsorption-catalysis trade-offs in individual inorganic or organic catalyst systems by integrating polysulfide confinement with accelerated reaction kinetics. Consequently, Li-S batteries achieve exceptional rate capability (>760 mAh g⁻¹ at 8C), extended cyclability (>80 % capacity retention over 500 cycles), and practical operation under high sulfur loading (5.2 mg cm⁻²). This work establishes a new strategy to boost Li-S cell performance based on the incorporation of organic redox mediator coupling inorganic catalysts by ligand functionalization.

1. Introduction

Lithium-sulfur (Li-S) batteries deliver a theoretical energy density of 2600 Wh kg⁻¹ and utilize abundant, low-cost sulfur, making them promising for next-generation storage systems [1]. The cell operates through multi-step redox reactions between elemental sulfur (S₈) and the final discharge product (Li₂S), yielding high specific capacity [2]. However, soluble lithium polysulfide intermediates (LiPSs, Li₂S_n, 4 ≤ n ≤ 8) generated during cycling readily dissolve in the electrolyte and migrate between the cathode and anode. This phenomenon, known as the "shuttle effect", leads to rapid capacity decay and high self-discharge rates [3]. Additionally, the insulating nature of Li₂S slows its nucleation and dissolution, while surface accumulation blocks Li⁺ transport [4].

Although strategies like physical confinement and chemical adsorption have been developed to suppress polysulfide migration, LiPSs accumulation in the cathode region increases electrolyte viscosity and deteriorates kinetic performance [5]. Thus, catalytic conversion strategies to accelerate LiPSs redox kinetics, particularly the rate-limiting liquid-solid processes like Li₂S nucleation/dissolution, are critical for enhancing battery performance [6–8]. Consequently, developing catalysts that can simultaneously ensure strong polysulfide adsorption and promote rapid catalytic conversion remains a key research priority in advancing Li-S battery technology [9,10].

Polar two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs), valued for their polysulfide adsorption capability, good electrical conductivity, and catalytic activity, have been widely explored as

* Corresponding author at: Catalonia Institute for Energy Research-IREC, Sant Adrià de Besòs, 08930, Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain.

** Corresponding authors at: College of Materials Science and Engineering, Fuzhou University, Fuzhou 350108, China.

E-mail addresses: chaoqizhang@fzu.edu.cn (C. Zhang), acabot@irec.cat (A. Cabot), hbzhan@fzu.edu.cn (H. Zhan).

electrocatalysts to accelerate polysulfide conversion and suppress shuttling [11–13]. Among TMDs, vanadium diselenide (VSe_2) is particularly attractive due to its sulfiphilic nature, intrinsic metallic conductivity, and relatively large interlayer spacing, offering pathways to high theoretical capacity and energy density [14–17]. VSe_2 can effectively adsorb LiPSs and promote Li_2S nucleation via exposed vanadium-rich edges [18]. However, the basal planes, chemically inert owing to saturated coordination [19], cover most of the surface and limit active-site exposure. Although reducing crystal size to increase edge-site density can enhance chemisorption [20], the challenging synthesis of VSe_2 nanocrystals limits their scalability. Although cation-doped or anion-deficient VSe_2 can enhance LiPSs adsorption and conversion activity, the impact of excessive heteroatom incorporation or defect formation on structural stability requires further investigation [21–23]. Similarly, heterostructures that integrate strong adsorption capability with catalytic activity, can improve LiPSs retention and accelerate Li–S redox reactions [24]. However, the intricate and energy-intensive fabrication of heterostructures often conflicts with the cost advantage of lithium-sulfur batteries. Overall, advancing high-performance Li–S batteries with VSe_2 catalysts requires the development of simpler and more efficient strategies that simultaneously maximize polysulfide retention and catalytic activity.

Recently, the introduction of redox mediators (RMs) has emerged as a promising strategy for operating Li–S batteries under harsh conditions (e.g., high sulfur loading, high current density, lean electrolyte) [7]. RMs undergo reversible redox reactions during cycling, acting as electron-hole transfer agents or generating new reactive intermediates, thereby optimizing performance and prolonging lifespan [25,26]. Among these, thiol-based chemistry, leveraging the strong affinity of the –SH group for sulfur species, has attracted particular attention in Li–S systems. Thiol-based organic molecules actively interact with LiPSs during cycling, promoting rapid sulfur species conversion and enhancing reaction kinetics. Studies confirm that organic dithiol additives form thiolates during cycling, establishing stable S–S bonds with polysulfides to alter redox pathways and inhibit shuttling [27–30]. However, while dissolved RMs benefit homogeneous reactions, their inherent migration between electrodes (“self-shuttling”) can lead to detrimental effects such as anode corrosion, while the absence of a direct electron-transfer pathway during the redox process further limits their efficiency [31,32].

Given the ability of thiol groups to both repair defects and functionalize TMDs [21], thiol-based RMs are highly complementary to VSe_2 for efficient polysulfide conversion catalysis. Anchoring dithiol RMs onto VSe_2 provides a dual benefit: suppressing self-shuttling and activating the otherwise inert basal planes, thereby enhancing polysulfide adsorption and accelerating catalytic conversion.

Herein, we report an organic–inorganic catalytic interface fabricated by a one-step ligand modification process (Scheme 1): ethanedithiol

(EDT) is grafted onto VSe_2 to yield a novel composite material (SH- VSe_2), which is then laminated onto a polypropylene (PP) separator (PP@SH- VSe_2) and functions as an interlayer. The short-chain dithiol is flexibly anchored, leaving sufficient –SH groups free to act as RMs while maintaining high turnover frequency [33,34]. Combined experimental results and density functional theory (DFT) calculations reveal three synergistic effects: 1) EDT coordination tailors the VSe_2 electronic structure, enhancing both LiPSs adsorption and intrinsic catalytic activity; 2) acting as a redox mediator, the non-coordinated thiol group in EDT transforms into thiolate (–SLi) during discharge, substantially reducing the nucleation and dissolution energy barriers of Li_2S and markedly accelerating liquid-to-solid conversion kinetics; and 3) immobilization of EDT on VSe_2 prevents RM self-shuttling while providing a direct electron-transfer pathway to the mediator for rapid redox reactions. Consequently, the PP@SH- VSe_2 separator achieves simultaneous polysulfide immobilization and accelerated catalytic conversion, delivering Li–S cells with exceptional rate capability and cycle life.

2. Results and discussion

VSe_2 was first synthesized via a minor modification of a reported route [35], then ultrasonically coordinated with ethanedithiol to yield SH- VSe_2 . Fig. 1a, b and S1 present the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of SH- VSe_2 and VSe_2 . Both materials exhibit a rod-like morphology self-assembled from nanosheets, indicating that EDT grafting preserves the microstructure. SH- VSe_2 exhibits an identical XRD pattern to that of VSe_2 (Fig. 1c). High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) images of SH- VSe_2 and VSe_2 (Fig. 1d and S2) further confirm the consistency of their fundamental crystal structure. The measured lattice fringes of 2.62 Å (Figure S3) correspond to the (011) plane of the 1T-phase VSe_2 crystal. High-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) imaging with corresponding energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) elemental mapping (Fig. 1e) evidences uniform Se, V, and S distributions across the nanosheets.

As shown in Fig. 1f, SH- VSe_2 exhibits a pronounced reduction in the photoluminescence (PL) band between 400 and 800 nm compared with VSe_2 , which is associated with surface defect-mediated sub-bandgap transition, indicating a lower defect density [36,37]. A concomitant blueshift of the peak position (from 530 nm in VSe_2 to 490 nm in SH- VSe_2) likely arises from an upward shift of interfacial state energy levels induced by EDT loading. High-resolution V 2p X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra (Fig. 1g and S4) show the characteristic splitting of V^{4+} and defect-state V orbitals into $2p_{1/2}$ and $2p_{3/2}$ peaks. For VSe_2 , the V^{4+} peaks are located at 516.6 eV ($2p_{3/2}$) and 523.9 eV ($2p_{1/2}$). In SH- VSe_2 , these peaks redshift ≈ 0.2 eV, consistent with electron donation from EDT’s –SH groups.

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration of the SH- VSe_2 functional layer facilitating the strong adsorption and fast conversion of LiPSs in a Li–S battery.

Fig. 1. Structural characterization. (a-b) SEM images, (d) HRTEM image with the corresponding FFT profile and a magnified HRTEM image detail of the red squared area in the insets, and (e) HAADF-STEM with corresponding elemental mapping images of SH-VSe₂ (scale bar: 100 nm). (c) XRD patterns, (f) PL spectra, and (g) V 2p XPS spectra of SH-VSe₂ and VSe₂. (h) Normalized XANES spectra of SH-VSe₂ and VSe₂ at the V K-edge with the V foil and VO₂ as reference samples. (i) V K-edge k^2 -weighted FT-EXAFS spectra of SH-VSe₂ and VSe₂ with phase-uncorrected. (j-l) WT plots for the V K-edge k^2 -weighted EXAFS signal for (j) V foil, (k) VSe₂, and (l) SH-VSe₂.

Fig. 1h presents V K-edge X-ray absorption near-edge structure (XANES) spectra for both materials, referenced against VO₂ (crystal) and vanadium foil standards. The absorption edge shift towards lower energy in SH-VSe₂ indicates a reduced vanadium oxidation state due to increased local electron density, attributed to electron donation from

EDT's thiol groups. This strong -SH coordination with exposed vanadium sites correlates with the significant decrease in defect-state V observed via XPS. The thiol introduction distorts the V center's local coordination environment from octahedral symmetry, enhancing the transition dipole moment and intensifying the white-line peak for SH-

VSe₂. Extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) spectra were k^2 -weighted Fourier transformed (FT) without phase correction to obtain the FT-EXAFS spectra (Fig. 1i). The peak at 2.2 Å corresponds to V–Se interactions. SH-VSe₂ exhibits a slight upward shift in this peak position due to lattice distortion from V–S coordination. Wavelet transform (WT) analysis of the k^2 -weighted EXAFS (Fig. 1j, l) shows coupling between the first nearest-neighbor V–Se coordination and the V–S coordination in SH-VSe₂, contrasting with VSe₂. This effect stems from the large scattering amplitude of lighter atoms at low k values [38] and the smaller ionic radius of S²⁻ versus Se²⁻, causing a partial redshift in the region.

Thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) shows a 3.3 wt % mass loss at ≈ 200 °C for SH-VSe₂ (Figure S5), matching the 2.2 wt % S content from EDS (Figure S6) and confirming EDT uptake. Furthermore, XRD patterns and visual inspection after 15-day exposure to high-humidity air

(Figure S7) demonstrate significantly enhanced environmental stability for SH-VSe₂ compared to pristine VSe₂.

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed to elucidate the ligand effect mechanism of EDT. The molecular electrostatic potential (Fig. 2a) shows a pronounced potential difference across the EDT molecule, indicating strong polarity that facilitates spontaneous orientation and potentially superior adsorption toward polysulfides on the VSe₂ surface. Negative lobes around its sulfur atoms act as electron donors and potential Li-binding sites. Differential charge density analysis (Fig. 2b, c) reveals electron depletion around EDT (blue) concomitant with accumulation at EDT anchoring sites on VSe₂ (red). Bader charge quantification demonstrates that each EDT molecule donates 1.88 electrons to the VSe₂ supercell, consistent with XPS and XAFS analyses. The cross-sectional 2D differential charge density map (Fig. 2d,

Fig. 2. Characterization of adsorption performance for polysulfides. (a) Molecular electrostatic potential of EDT. (b) Top view and (c) side view of charge-density difference plots of EDT interacting with VSe₂. Red and blue isosurfaces represent electron accumulation and electron depletion at an isosurface cutoff of 0.002 e⁻/Bohr³. (d) 2D projection of charge density contour of SH-VSe₂ at the α section as seen in Figure (c). (e) DOS plot of SH-VSe₂ and VSe₂. (f) Optical photograph of the Li₂S₄ adsorption test. (g) V 2p XPS patterns of SH-VSe₂ before and after Li₂S₄ adsorption. (h) Optical photographs of the LiPSs permeation test in H-type cells.

α -section from Fig. 2c) shows distinct electron density accumulation (red region) around V atoms at EDT-anchored sites. This electronic structure modulation is crucial for enhancing VSe₂'s catalytic functionality, as shown below.

Density of states (DOS) calculations further probe EDT's influence on

VSe₂'s electronic structure. The total DOS (TDOS, Fig. 2e) exhibits metallic characteristics, with non-zero states at the Fermi level in both materials. Projected DOS (PDOS) analysis reveals V d-orbitals dominate near the Fermi level. Compared to p-orbitals, d-orbitals possess higher energy levels and greater influence on electron localization,

Fig. 3. Catalytic activity and Li₂S conversion kinetics. (a) C_{dl} of SH-VSe₂ and VSe₂ catalysts. (b) CV curves of symmetric cells employing SH-VSe₂, VSe₂ and Super P electrodes at 10.0 mV s⁻¹. (c) Dimensionless transient (symbols), i_m (peak current), and t_m (time to reach peak current) compared with theoretical growth models. (d) Li₂S nucleation i-t curve. (e) SEM images of the electrodes after nucleation, showing Li₂S deposition morphology (scale bar: 500 nm). (f) Li₂S dissolution i-t curve. (g) Schematic diagrams of nucleation and growth models of Li₂S on different electrodes.

characteristic of TMD catalyst-polysulfide interactions [39]. While pristine VSe_2 's V d-orbital PDOS shows multiple near-zero density points, SH- VSe_2 exhibits significantly increased density at these points due to hybridization with EDT's 2p orbitals. This strong ligand field effect yields a more continuous DOS distribution (versus discrete peaks in VSe_2), promoting electron delocalization. Consequently, electrical conductivity increases (confirmed by Figure S8) and electron transfer accelerates during polysulfide conversion, potentially enabling ultrahigh-rate performance. Furthermore, this ligand effect shifts the d-band center (ϵ_d) upward from -2.42 eV (VSe_2) to -2.25 eV (SH- VSe_2). The resulting reduction in antibonding orbital electron population favors strong LiPSs adsorption [40].

To validate DFT predictions, we experimentally evaluated its adsorption capacities towards Li_2S_4 , as a representative LiPSs, to determine the ability of a separator coating against the shuttle effect. Static adsorption tests (Fig. 2f) confirm SH- VSe_2 outperforms all controls: after 12 h in Li_2S_4 solution, the supernatant is colorless and the 400–500 nm UV-vis band is fully suppressed. XPS analysis reveals mechanistic insights: When SH- VSe_2 adsorbs Li_2S_4 (Lewis base), its V 2p peak shifts ≈ 0.2 eV toward lower binding energy (Fig. 2g), indicating effective chemisorption. The microstructure and physical properties of the modified separator are critical to its function. As shown in Figure S9, the SH- VSe_2 and VSe_2 layers are uniformly coated on the PP substrate with a thickness of approximately 12.8 μm . This well-defined, thin layer is crucial for minimizing the diffusion path of Li^+ ions and directly translate to superior interfacial and ion-transport properties. Contact-angle measurements (Figure S10) show electrolyte wettability improves from 28.3° (PP) to 14.4° (PP@ VSe_2) and 4.2° (PP@SH- VSe_2), lowering interfacial resistance and facilitating Li^+ transport. Ion mobility is essential for lithium metal batteries [41,42]. This intimate contact with the electrolyte, combined with the optimized thickness, facilitates rapid ion transport. Consequently, the PP@SH- VSe_2 separator achieves a high ionic conductivity of 1.42 $mS\ cm^{-1}$ (Figure S11), which is significantly higher than that of the PP@ VSe_2 (0.91 $mS\ cm^{-1}$) and pristine PP separator (0.49 $mS\ cm^{-1}$). H-cell diffusion assays (Fig. 2h) visually quantify shuttle suppression: after 12 h, the right chamber remains colorless for PP@SH- VSe_2 , whereas PP@ VSe_2 and bare PP allow pronounced polysulfide migration.

The electrochemical performance of different catalysts was evaluated to assess their catalytic effects on Li-S reactions. Cyclic voltammetry (CV)-derived double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}) measurements determined the electrochemical active surface area (ECSA) [43]. As shown in Fig. 3a (with fitting data from Figure S12), the organic-inorganic hybrid SH- VSe_2 exhibited a substantially higher C_{dl} value of 1.03 $mF\ cm^{-2}$ compared to pristine VSe_2 (0.2 $mF\ cm^{-2}$). This enhancement indicates substantially increased active site density despite similar surface morphology and specific area (Figure S13), confirming EDT-mediated activation of VSe_2 's inert basal planes. Symmetric cell analysis further probed catalytic kinetics. At 10.0 $mV\ s^{-1}$ in Li_2S_6 -containing electrolyte (Fig. 3b), SH- VSe_2 cells exhibited higher current density than VSe_2 and Super P, demonstrating accelerated LiPSs redox kinetics and effective shuttle suppression. The reduced peak separation (ΔE_p) indicates lower overpotential and superior reversibility.

Li_2S deposition experiments (Fig. 3d) quantified conversion kinetics for the rate-limiting sulfur reduction reaction step [44]. SH- VSe_2 achieved peak deposition in just 300 s, faster than VSe_2 (745 s) and Super P (1605 s). Corresponding deposition capacities were 390.76 $mAh\ g^{-1}$ (Faraday's law, sulfur-based) for SH- VSe_2 versus 276.35 $mAh\ g^{-1}$ (VSe_2) and 216.59 $mAh\ g^{-1}$ (PP), with nucleation current analysis confirming enhanced kinetics.

Four classical Li_2S deposition models (2D instantaneous: 2DI; 2D progressive: 2DP; 3D instantaneous: 3DI; 3D progressive: 3DP) are widely applied in Li-S research. Dimensionless current-time transient analysis (Fig. 3c) further elucidates Li_2S nucleation behavior across different electrodes [45]. Combined with Li_2S SEM morphology (Fig. 3e

and S14), distinct nucleation/growth patterns emerge (Fig. 3g). The time to maximum nucleation current (t_m) follows the relationship: [46]

$$t_m = \left(\frac{2}{Ak^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (1)$$

where A means the nucleation rate constant ($cm^{-2}\ s^{-1}$), k represents the growth rate ($cm\ s^{-1}$). This inverse correlation indicates that t_m decreases with higher nucleation density and faster lateral growth.

Smaller t_m values confirmed slower lateral growth rates, favoring 3D Li_2S deposition that facilitates electrolyte infiltration and reduces nucleation barriers [47,48]. Super P exhibited 2DP-2DI nucleation with nonuniform distribution due to nonpolar physical adsorption and poor catalytic activity [49], while SH- VSe_2 and VSe_2 initiated 3DI growth via abundant nucleation sites. Beyond the peak nucleation time, the nucleation model adjusts due to constraints from surface site passivation, electron transport efficiency, and Li^+ diffusion kinetics. Crucially, SH- VSe_2 sustains 3D nucleation (3DI-3DP mode at $t/t_m > 2$) by delaying passivation through richer active sites, whereas VSe_2 transition to a mixed 3DP-2DI pattern.

Dissolution tests (Fig. 3f) revealed SH- VSe_2 's maximum capacity (802 $mAh\ g^{-1}$) and unique 2.15 V oxidation peak (Figure S15), indicating reduced energy barriers. The enhanced initial current response (Figure S16) confirmed superior electron transfer. These results demonstrate SH- VSe_2 's exceptional dual-phase conversion kinetics, enabled by synergistic EDT-mediated catalysis at organic-inorganic interfaces that predicts significantly accelerated redox kinetics when integrated into Li-S batteries.

Coin cells were assembled using sulfur cathodes (70 % S in C/S composite, Figure S17), lithium anodes, and modified separators to evaluate battery performance. CV curves (0.1 $mV\ s^{-1}$, Fig. 4a) of PP@SH- VSe_2 cells show typical discharge peaks at 2.31 V (I, $S_8 \rightarrow Li_2S_n$) and 2.05 V (II, $Li_2S_n \rightarrow Li_2S_2/Li_2S$). While the PP cell exhibits a broad anodic peak, PP@ VSe_2 and PP@SH- VSe_2 cells show split oxidation peaks at ~ 2.35 V (III, $Li_2S \rightarrow Li_2S_n$) and ~ 2.40 V (IV, $Li_2S_n \rightarrow S_8$), indicating accelerated oxidation kinetics. PP@SH- VSe_2 exhibits stronger peak currents and lower polarization (Figure S18), signifying faster kinetics. Notably, only PP@SH- VSe_2 displays an additional redox couple at ~ 2.17 V. This observation aligns with previous reports based on unique chemical reaction of thiol-based additives in Li-S batteries [29, 30, 50, 51]. Sulfhydryl groups are electrochemical active sites in this process, accompanied by the generation of S-S bonds /-S-Li units. The electrochemical signature should be attributed to capacity contribution from lithiation reaction of thiol groups, where lithiated -S-Li group modulates polysulfide conversion, confirming EDT's RM function. We assembled a cell with SH- VSe_2 cathode and discharged it to 2.0 V, a potential at which the -S-Li intermediate is expected to be maximally formed according to our electrochemical data. The cell was then disassembled in an inert atmosphere, and the SH- VSe_2 cathode was thoroughly rinsed with DOL/DME solvent and transferred for *ex-situ* XPS analysis. The high-resolution S 2p spectrum reveals a decisive shift (Figure S19): In the pristine SH- VSe_2 , the S 2p signal is dominated by a doublet at 163.3 eV (164.4 eV) and 162.5 eV (163.6 eV), which are characteristic of the -SH and -SV in the anchored EDT molecule [52]. In the discharged SH- VSe_2 , the -SH doublet has vanished and is replaced by a new doublet centered at a binding energy of 161.5 eV (162.6 eV), which is characteristic of the -S-Li specie [53]. By comparing the discharge curves of cells with PP@SH- VSe_2 and PP@ VSe_2 cathode (Figure S20), we can isolate the capacity uniquely attributable to the lithiation reaction of the EDT's -SH groups. The sulfur-free cell delivers only ~ 7.8 $mAh\ g^{-1}$, confirming the EDT's RM role. Each EDT molecule transfer electrons to the sulfur species throughout the redox process.

The robust anchoring of EDT on the VSe_2 surface, achieved through the formation of a stable V-S covalent bond, is crucial for preventing the "self-shuttling" of the RMs. The stability of this coordination is confirmed by control experiments detected by XPS and EDS (Figure S21-S22),

Fig. 4. Analysis of electrochemical performance. (a) CV curves of the PP (yellow), PP@VSe₂ (blue), and PP@SH-VSe₂ (red) cells at 0.1 mV s⁻¹ scan rate. (b) CV curves of the PP@SH-VSe₂ cell at various scan rates. (c) Lithium-ion diffusion coefficient. (d) CV curves of PP@SH-VSe₂ at different temperatures. (e) Relation between CV peak (II) current and temperature for the PP, PP@VSe₂, and PP@SH-VSe₂ cells, respectively. (f) GCD profiles at 0.1C. (g) Corresponding enlarged part of the GCD curves at 0.1C. (h) Gibbs free energy of the generation of -SLi species with Li₂S₄/Li₂S₆ adsorbed. (i) Optimized geometric configuration of S species adsorbed on SLi-VSe₂/SLi-VSe₂. (j) Charge-density difference and interfacial electron transfer of Li₂S₄ interacting with SH-VSe₂ (left) and VSe₂ (right). Red and blue isosurfaces represent electron accumulation and electron depletion at an isosurface cutoff of 0.002 e⁻/Bohr³. (k) Adsorption energies of various sulfur species. (l) Free energy profiles for the reduction of sulfur species on different catalysts. (m) Migration path and (n) energy barrier profiles of Li₂S decomposition on SLi-VSe₂ and VSe₂.

which show negligible leaching of sulfur species from the SH-VSe₂ composite after prolonged solvent immersion and extended cell rest. Meanwhile, EDS analysis of the lithium counter electrode from this cell showed a negligible sulfur signal (Figure S23), confirming the exceptional stability of the EDT anchoring on the VSe₂ surface.

Reaction kinetics were analyzed through scan-rate-dependent CV (Fig. 4b and S24) based on Randles-Sevcik analysis (Figure S25). Using the Randles-Sevcik equation, Li⁺ diffusion coefficients (D_{Li^+}) were calculated: [54]

$$I_p = (2.69 \times 10^5)n^{1.5}AD_{Li^+}^{0.5}C_{Li^+}v^{0.5} \quad (2)$$

where I_p = the peak current (A), n = electron number, A = electrode area (cm²), C_{Li^+} = Li⁺ concentration (mol cm⁻³), and v = scan rate (V s⁻¹). PP@SH-VSe₂ achieves significantly higher D_{Li^+} at peaks I (9.77×10^{-8} cm² s⁻¹), II (35.88×10^{-8} cm² s⁻¹), and III (58.56×10^{-8} cm² s⁻¹) versus controls (Fig. 4c), indicating enhanced ion transport and conversion kinetics.

Temperature-dependent CV measurements (Fig. 4d and S26) were performed to analyze the reaction kinetics, with particular focus on peak II — the primary capacity contributor corresponding to the Li₂S₄/Li₂S conversion process. The Arrhenius equation was employed to fit this peak, enabling determination of the electrochemical reaction's activation energy parameters [55].

$$i\alpha A \times e^{-E_a/RT} \quad (3)$$

where E_a is the activation energy, R is the gas constant, A is a pre-exponential factor, and T is temperature.

The fitting results (Fig. 4e) show that the PP@VSe₂ cell exhibits a substantially lower activation barrier (11.74 kJ mol⁻¹) compared to the PP cell (20.53 kJ mol⁻¹). Remarkably, the PP@SH-VSe₂ cell exhibits an ultralow barrier of only 6.57 kJ mol⁻¹, demonstrating that EDT-functionalized VSe₂ significantly reduce the activation energy during the liquid-solid reaction in Li-S batteries, thereby accelerating the overall redox reaction kinetics.

Fig. 4f presents the galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) profiles of Li-S batteries with different separators at 0.1C. The voltage gap ΔE between the oxidation plateau and the second reduction plateau at 50 % discharge capacity represents the polarization potential [56], serving as an indicator of LiPs conversion kinetics. The PP@SH-VSe₂ cell delivers the highest initial capacity (1592 mAh g⁻¹) and lowest polarization (121 mV), demonstrating SH-VSe₂'s effectiveness in promoting full sulfur utilization and favorable reaction kinetics. This performance surpasses PP@VSe₂ (1470 mAh g⁻¹, 142 mV) and pristine PP cells (1106 mAh g⁻¹, 195 mV).

Notably, PP@SH-VSe₂ exhibits an initial discharge plateau at about 2.35–2.30 V ($S_8 \rightarrow Li_2S_n$), and a distinctive plateau at 2.20–2.15 V ($-SH + e^- + Li^+ \rightarrow -SLi$), correlating with the additional reduction peak in CV tests. During subsequent discharge, at the onset of the final plateau ($Li_2S_4 \rightarrow Li_2S_2/Li_2S$), PP@SH-VSe₂ shows a nucleation overpotential of 24 mV (Figure S27), significantly lower than PP@VSe₂ (28 mV) and PP (38 mV).

During charging, the PP cell requires a high potential of 2.35 V, whereas PP@VSe₂ and PP@SH-VSe₂ initiate Li₂S oxidation at 2.22 V and 2.15 V, respectively (Figure S28), confirming the catalysts' barrier-lowering effect. PP@SH-VSe₂ exhibits an exceptionally low Li₂S dissolution overpotential of 4 mV — an order of magnitude lower than PP@VSe₂ (28 mV) and PP (78 mV) (Fig. 4g) — highlighting the enhanced catalytic activity achieved through surface functionalization. Remarkably, PP@VSe₂ exhibits a secondary oxidation step at 2.27 V, while PP@SH-VSe₂ completes oxidation in a single step at a lower potential. These results demonstrate that EDT modification not only activates organic-inorganic interfaces but also functions as a redox mediator, facilitating electron transfer and redox kinetics.

DFT calculation results are consistent with these electrochemical observations. As key intermediates bridging sulfur reduction stages,

Li₂S₄ and Li₂S₆ critically influence polysulfide shuttling. Previous work by Duan et al. demonstrated that Li₂S₆ originates from Li₂S₄ disproportionation [2], with delayed kinetics manifesting as voltage plateaus at 2.25–2.11 V in CV profiles. The additional reduction peak at 2.17 V in this work indicates -SLi formation during Li₂S₆/Li₂S₄ adsorption. Reaction free energy calculations (Fig. 4h) reveal that Li₂S₄ adsorption leads to spontaneous -SLi generation ($\Delta G = -0.27$ eV), in contrast to the endergonic process for Li₂S₆ adsorption accompanied -SLi generation ($\Delta G = 0.22$ eV).

Catalytic conversion pathways are mapped in Fig. 4i. Differential charge density analysis (Fig. 4j) shows enhanced charge accumulation (red) and depletion (blue) at Li₂S₄/SLi-VSe₂ interfaces versus Li₂S₄/VSe₂, indicating stronger interactions. Bader charge quantification confirms greater electron transfer from Li₂S₄ to SLi-VSe₂ (0.56 e⁻/supercell) than to VSe₂ (0.49 e⁻/supercell). Adsorption energies across lithiation stages (Fig. 4k, optimized geometries in Figure S29–S30) demonstrate consistently stronger binding for SLi-VSe₂/SH-VSe₂, aligning with experimental adsorption tests and confirming superior shuttle suppression.

Sulfur reduction kinetics were analyzed through Gibbs free energy landscapes (Fig. 4l). The rate-determining step ($Li_2S_2 \rightarrow Li_2S$) exhibits a 0.67 eV barrier on VSe₂, reduced to 0.51 eV on SLi-VSe₂. For Li₂S oxidation (Fig. 4m), decomposition barriers decrease from 1.01 eV (VSe₂) to 0.75 eV (SLi-VSe₂) (Fig. 4n). These theoretical results corroborate experimental data, confirming that EDT modification enhances shuttle suppression while SLi-VSe₂ formation dramatically reduces transformation barriers. This validates EDT's critical role as RM and directly links reduced Li₂S nucleation/dissolution barriers to SLi-VSe₂ interfaces.

In-situ galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analyses were used to systematically evaluate the impact of catalyst-modified separators on electrochemical kinetics throughout charge/discharge cycles. Voltage-time profiles during operation are shown in Fig. 5a, with GITT pulse sequences (Fig. 5b) detailed in the Supporting Information. Simultaneously acquired EIS spectra (Fig. 5c) enabled dynamic monitoring. The internal resistance during Li₂S nucleation/activation was quantified by the voltage gap (ΔiR) between closed-circuit voltage (CCV) and quasi-open-circuit voltage (QOCV) [57]. As shown in Fig. 5d, PP@SH-VSe₂ exhibits earlier Li₂S nucleation onset (28.5 % state of discharge, SOD) and lower ΔiR (0.032 V) compared to PP@VSe₂ (29.4 % SOD, 0.046 V). During charging (Fig. 5e), significantly reduced resistance at Li₂S activation points confirms EDT-mediated acceleration of oxidation kinetics. These results demonstrate reduced polarization and faster dynamic response during solid-liquid conversions in PP@SH-VSe₂ due to EDT's RM effect.

Fig. 5f–g presents the evolution of Nyquist plots during discharge. At 0 % SOD, PP@SH-VSe₂ shows higher impedance, attributed to sluggish diffusion kinetics of solid oxidation products in the fully charged state. The dramatic increase in resistance (the mid-to-low frequency region) for the PP@VSe₂ cell at the end of discharge is attributed to the formation of a passivating Li₂S layer, which induces severe concentration polarization (η_{con} , Fig. 5b) [58,59]. Although Li₂S nucleation begins earlier, the solid-state conversion in the final stage leads to rapid accumulation of insulating Li₂S. This dense layer blocks ion transport pathways and, coupled with the depletion of soluble polysulfide reactants, causes the observed resistance surge. In contrast, the PP@SH-VSe₂ cell mitigates this issue through its superior catalytic activity, which promotes a porous 3D Li₂S growth and ensures more complete conversion. Consequently, concentration polarization and interfacial resistance remain low throughout the entire discharge process (Figure S31).

Distribution of relaxation times (DRT) analysis of *in-situ* EIS dynamically monitors reaction barrier evolution (Fig. 5h). Characteristic peaks correspond to specific processes: P4 for cathode charge transfer [60], P6 for Li⁺ diffusion in Li₂S₂, and P7 for Li⁺ diffusion in S₈/Li₂S [61], respectively. P4 peaks at ~25 % SOD (end of first plateau,

Fig. 5. Analysis of reaction kinetics. (a) GITT profiles of cells with PP@SH-VSe₂ and PP@VSe₂ separator. (b) GITT process and (c) EIS spectra measured before each rest step relaxation (taking 10 % SOD of PP@SH-VSe₂ cell as an example). (d, e) Internal resistances of the PP@SH-VSe₂ and PP@VSe₂ cell relative to the normalized discharge (d) and charge (e) time. (f, g) In situ EIS curves of each relaxation process of GITT. (h) DRT profile presented by PP@VSe₂ cell. (i, j) In-situ DRT analysis of (i) PP@SH-VSe₂ and (j) PP@VSe₂ cells according to in-situ GITT-EIS. (k) DRT curves of PP@SH-VSe₂ and PP@VSe₂ at 100 % SOD.

Figure S32), reflecting charge transfer inhibition from increased electrolyte viscosity [62]. P7 emerges at $\sim 25\%$ SOD (start of second plateau), intensifying near 100% SOD as Li_2S rapidly accumulates. The adjacent P6 peaks with maximum intensity at $\sim 85\%$ SOD, attributed to Li_2S_2 significant accumulation. Compared with PP@VSe_2 , PP@SH-VSe_2 reduces the accumulation of Li_2S_2 , which is more conducive to the formation of Li_2S as the final discharge product [63,64]. The P7 peak during charging reflects Li^+ diffusion resistance in solid-phase sulfur. SH-VSe_2 catalyst promotes more complete oxidation, yielding higher

sulfur conversion to final solid oxidation products at the cathode, thus intensifying the P7 peak at 0% SOD compared to PP@VSe_2 batteries. At 100% SOD (Fig. 5k), PP@SH-VSe_2 exhibits substantially lower overall resistance across the DRT spectrum, demonstrating faster charge transfer and optimized catalyst-active material-electrolyte interfaces through thiol-modified catalysis.

Electrochemical performance evaluation of Li-S batteries with different separators revealed significant advantages for PP@SH-VSe_2 . Fig. 6a demonstrates superior rate capability across 0.1C – 8C current

Fig. 6. Performance of Li-S batteries. (a) Rate performance of Li-S batteries at current densities from 0.1 to 8 C. (b) GCD profiles during the rate test of SH-VSe_2 cell. (c) Energy efficiency of different cells at different current densities. (d) Cycling performance of Li-S batteries with different separators. (e) Rate performance of SH-VSe_2 cell with high S loading. (f) Cycling performance of SH-VSe_2 cell with high S loading and low E/S ratio. (g) Cycling performances at 0.2C of a pouch cell based on PP@SH-VSe_2 separator and (h) Optical photograph of an "FZU" panel contained 30 red LEDs powered by a pouch cell based on PP@SH-VSe_2 separator.

densities. Leveraging a unique organic–inorganic synergistic mechanism, PP@SH-VSe₂ maintains substantially higher capacities than PP@VSe₂ and pristine PP counterparts. Remarkably, at 8C, PP@SH-VSe₂ delivers 765 mAh g⁻¹, dramatically exceeding PP@VSe₂ (84 mAh g⁻¹) and PP (negligible capacity). When returned to 0.2C, it recovers 1210 mAh g⁻¹, confirming excellent reversibility. GCD profiles (Fig. 6b) show well-preserved discharge plateaus for PP@SH-VSe₂ across all rates, while PP@VSe₂ and PP exhibit plateau distortion at high currents (Figure S33). Round-trip energy efficiency (E_E) analysis, calculated by the ratio of energy output/input ($E = \int UI dt$) [65], highlights PP@SH-VSe₂'s exceptional performance (Fig. 6c). It maintains >83.5 % E_E even at 8C, significantly surpassing PP@VSe₂ (75.8 %) and PP (56.1 % at 3C). Long-term cycling at 1C (Fig. 6d, S34) shows PP@SH-VSe₂'s initial capacity of 974 mAh g⁻¹ with 81.5 % retention after 500 cycles (0.043 % decay/cycle), which is vastly superior to PP@VSe₂ (0.18 %/cycle over 250 cycles) and PP (0.38 %/cycle over 120 cycles). Post-cycling analysis (Figure S35) reveals smooth lithium anodes with minimal sulfur signals for PP@SH-VSe₂, confirming effective shuttle suppression and stable EDT coordination at operating conditions.

The assessment of commercial viability requires testing cells with high sulfur loading (5.2 mg cm⁻²). At 0.1C and 2C, the capacities of the high sulfur loading cell reach 1231 and 831 mAh g⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 6e). Additionally, under lean electrolyte conditions (E/S = 7.6 mL g⁻¹), PP@SH-VSe₂ delivers 845 mAh g⁻¹ initial capacity at 0.5C with 82.6 % retention after 152 cycles (0.12 % decay/cycle) while exhibiting well-defined plateaus (Fig. 6f and S36). Even at extremely low E/S (4.8 mL g⁻¹) condition, PP@SH-VSe₂ cell delivers a high initial discharge capacity of 778 mAh g⁻¹ at 0.2C and exhibits excellent cycling stability, retaining 81.2 % of its capacity after 40 cycles (Figure S37). Comparative analysis (Table S1) confirms PP@SH-VSe₂'s exceptional performance among VSe₂- and thiol-based systems. Practical validation using pouch cells (E/S = 7.3 mL g⁻¹, Figure S38) achieves 1254 mAh g⁻¹ at 0.2C with >75 stable cycles (Fig. 6g). Finally, the successful operation of a 30-LED panel (Fig. 6h) demonstrates potential for practical deployment.

3. Conclusions

An EDT-modified VSe₂ (SH-VSe₂) organic–inorganic catalyst was developed via a facile ligand-functionalization method. This catalyst was applied at the cathode side of Li–S battery separators. SH-VSe₂ synergistically combines the strong catalytic activity of TMDs with the reaction-modulating capability of organic RMs. Structural characterization confirms EDT coordination induces local VSe₂ lattice distortion, optimizes the VSe₂ electronic structure, and upshifts the V d-band center, enhancing LiPs chemisorption and catalytic conversion. Critically, in-situ generation of –SLi on SH-VSe₂ during discharge, facilitated by EDT acting as an RM, drastically reduces the energy barriers for Li₂S nucleation and dissolution, accelerating solid-liquid conversion kinetics. These advantages enable PP@SH-VSe₂-based Li–S batteries to achieve exceptional rate capability (765 mAh g⁻¹ at 8C), cycling stability (0.043 % decay/cycle over 500 cycles at 1C), and practical viability in high S loading 5.2 mg cm⁻² and low electrolyte usage conditions. This "organic ligand modification–electronic structure modulation–synergistic catalysis" strategy provides a versatile approach for engineering functionalized organic–inorganic catalysts, advancing Li–S batteries toward cost-effective, high-performance energy storage.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kaifu Lin: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Chaoqi Zhang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Ban Fei:** Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jing Yu:**

Methodology, Formal analysis. **Canhuang Li:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Qidi Chen:** Visualization, Methodology. **Daoping Cai:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Baisheng Sa:** Software, Methodology. **Wenwei Chen:** Investigation. **Dawei Yang:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Jordi Arbiol:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Andreu Cabot:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Hongbing Zhan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.ensm.2025.104803.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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